

IR42, IR2823-399-5-6, IR9129-163-3-2-2, IR9129-192-2-3-5, and IR2307-247-2-2-3. Nematodes were found in all samples.

Populations in 50-gram root samples

of local varieties ranged from 12 to 380 at tillering, increasing to 50 to 7,000 at flowering, and to 300 to 7,500 at ripening. In the second crop, populations at transplanting were 204 to 9,000; at tiller-

ing, 860 to 11,200.

Populations in 100-ml soil samples averaged 71 throughout the sampling period, with a range of 5 to 450 nematodes. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Using check varieties to adjust visual scores for nonuniform soil drying in drought resistance field screening

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In many areas of monsoon Asia, the dry season allows use of irrigation (surface or sprinkler) to control timing (growth stage) and duration of water stress in drought resistance screening of germplasm in the field. But variability in soil drying results in problems in interpreting visual scores among entries. Using soil moisture measurements (tensiometers, gypsum blocks, or gravimetric sampling) to indicate relative soil water deficits within a field has inherent technical problems and is not generally satisfactory.

A method using frequently spaced check varieties to adjust or normalize field screening results for heterogeneity of soil drying has been developed.

Field screening for drought resistance was conducted in the 1980 dry season at the Klong Luang Rice Experiment Station, Thailand. Localized deviations of IR20 (susceptible check) and BKN6986-108-3 (local resistant check) from their overall means were used to adjust scores of entries in nearby plots. The figure illustrates the heterogeneity of soil drying across the field that was identified by the response of check varieties and deviations from their respective overall means.

Variation in soil drying across field is illustrated by changes in responses of IR20 (susceptible check) and BKN6986-108-3 (resistant check). IRRI.

Statistical analysis of original (A) and adjusted (B) visual drought resistance scores of 77 entries in 1980 dry season field screening for drought resistance at Klong Luang Rice Experiment Station, Thailand.

	$\frac{\sigma_v^2}{\sigma_E^2}$	CV (%)	F-value	DMRT (5%) discrimination range (no.)
A	0.5603	29.9	2.12**	A-G (7)
B	1.0377	24.0	3.08**	A-M (13)

At any place in the field, the average of the check varieties' deviations from their respective means was applied to the scores of adjacent entries, normalizing varietal response for soil moisture heterogeneity. The ratio of varietal variance (σ_v^2) to experimental variance (σ_E^2) was used in evaluating the capability of adjusted data to better differentiate entries. Adjusting the original visual drought resistance scores for field soil moisture conditions increased the σ_v^2/σ_E^2 ratio, decreased the CV, and increased the capability of Duncan's Multiple Range Test (5% level) to differentiate between entries (see table).

This method uses check varieties which are usually well known by the individual scorer to systematically cope with the problem of inherent variability in drought screening caused by non-

uniform soil physical properties or by inequity of irrigation water distribution. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Varietal tolerance for acid sulfate soils in North Vietnam

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Varieties were screened for acid sulfate soil tolerance during the 1977, 1978, and